

Concept Note: Multi-Objective Optimization of Inconel 718 Finish Turning

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Abstract. This concept note outlines an upcoming study on the finish turning of Inconel 718 using a DMG MORI CLX-350 CNC lathe. A Taguchi L27 orthogonal array is employed to investigate the effects of four cutting parameters: cutting speed (V_c : 30–70 m/min), feed rate (f_z : 0.1–0.3 mm/rev), depth of cut (a_p : 0.2–0.6 mm), and nose radius (r : 0.2–0.8 mm). Surface roughness (R_a), material removal rate (MRR), cutting forces, and tool wear will be measured as response variables. Support Vector Regression (SVR) will be applied to develop predictive models, while ANOVA will identify the statistical significance of each input factor. Subsequently, a multi-objective optimization will be conducted using the Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm III (NSGA-III) to simultaneously minimize R_a and tool wear, while maximizing MRR.

This early dissemination aims to share the methodology and modeling approach prior to full experimental execution and publication.

Keywords: Inconel 718, Finish Turning, SVR, Taguchi L27, ANOVA, NSGA-III, Multi-Objective Optimization, Machining

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1 Introduction

2 Methodology

3 Experimental Setup

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Discussion

5 Conclusion

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